

**USE OF FABRICS WITH ENHANCED PERFORMANCE
CHARACTERISTICS IN MANUFACTURING SPECIAL APPAREL FOR
OIL AND GAS INDUSTRY WORKERS.**

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Abstract:

This article provides complete information on material selection, justification and materials for the production of special clothes. Information about the classification processes of special clothes according to their application is given.

Key words: special clothes Skotchlayt, Momblan, Skotchlayt, Proban, Gidrofoyl

Due to the fact that special clothes are worn for a long time and are in constant contact with the human body, the materials used in making clothes are also required to be suitable for the human body. When choosing material for special clothing, protective equipment and the above features are taken into account. Clothing is not only a means of wearing, but the possibility of sewing fabrics in the production of sewing, its use is served by its durability and convenience. Fabrics used in sewing special clothes are also considered integrally related to the level of protection of the clothes and are divided into a number of groups: - special clothing fabrics for metallurgists (group 1) - special clothing fabrics for oil field workers (group 2) - for welders (svarshik) special clothing fabrics (group 3) are divided into the same types as special clothing fabrics (group 4) for workers in general production areas. Gases used in special clothes do not meet all requirements, those that are resistant to mechanical effects can absorb, transfer or retain liquid. Fire-resistant materials lose their integrity under the influence of bending and compression deformations. Those that are resistant to chemicals are less resistant to various mechanical effects. Special clothing fabric must directly meet the world standard requirements, quality indicators, regulatory legal documents of the material, types of raw materials [1]. For sewing special clothes, it is allowed to use fabrics woven from natural and mixed fibers. It is allowed to use clothes made of chemical fibers (materials) as outerwear for workers who work continuously (for more than 2 hours) at low temperatures. Below is information about a number of fabrics used in sewing special clothes. Special - a garment intended for the production of highly comfortable winter and summer special working clothes (suits, gowns, coveralls). In this clothing, people

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feel not only protected but also comfortable at work. Momblan is a special gas protection against high and low (from 400 to 600) temperature. Its distinctive feature is its lightness and small size. Manblan style clothes have special construction elements and are provided with conveniences at work. Tinsulet is an extremely lightweight, compact, micro-fiber heater that is widely used worldwide. Product of ZM company. Created 20 years ago. The fabric is made of thin synthetic fibers. The fiber is ten times thinner than that of conventional heaters. It is breathable and keeps heat well. Tinsulet has heat protection properties. After washing, it does not change its shape or size and does not stretch. Qakhraton provides full comfort even in cold weather. Scotchlite is a fabric made by adding a high-visibility microscopic glass lens. Scotchlite is a reflective material from car headlights. Scotchlite special clothing ensures high safety of workers. It can be felt even in the dark and protects from various unfortunate events. Hollofiber is a non-woven heater made of polyamide fibers acting as a twisted spiral spring. Holo fiber is characterized by air permeability despite its softness and high processing. Holo fiber, which is easy to clean, mixes, harmonizes and glues well with other fabrics. Proban is fire-resistant, produced in the Rhodia company, considered a leader among world technologies, provides fire protection, certified. 80-85% of global production is used as protective clothing. The fabric does not change under the influence of fire, the service life is extended. Even after a lot of use, it keeps its condition well. Flame retardant proban and oko-tex 100 standard certificate. It guarantees that the skin will not be damaged. Hydrofoil is a special foil produced by the Klopman company. This gas mask meets the requirements of EN 13034 and EN 368 in terms of protection against the effects of liquid, harmful chemicals. Limits the effect of water, oil and their mixtures in different proportions. Based on nanotechnologies, the layer covered by strong gas and liquid effects creates separate pieces without retaining it. Cordura is a water-resistant polyurethane coating and a special gasket made of thick nylon threads. The preparation of gas mixture is carried out in several stages, which allows high-quality, long-term use. Cordura melts at 260°C. Gazlama has high durability, friction, and is resistant to the effects of ultraviolet rays. Tyvek is a dense, thin, light and soft material. Produced by the Du Pont company, it captures small dust particles (up to 3 microns). Its further advantages are that it completely retains acid and alkali solutions up to 30%. This gauze is distinguished from others by the fact that it does not contain cotton fibers and silicon substances. The above company recommended Taikem C fabric by pouring polymer on the base, and Taikem F fabrics by lamination. The raw materials of this garment can protect against gas pressures of 2-5 barometers, splashing liquid and various mixtures of blood, respectively. Master universal ca 25 mbo c with antistatic yarn is designed for special summer suits and

corporate clothes. this fabric is intended for personnel working in closed buildings. It is worth noting that as a result of various treatments of the fabrics recommended for special clothes, the raw material does not protect, but may emit various harmful substances. Therefore, it is necessary to pass gas tests and recommend it for special clothes.

About approving model standards for free provision of special clothing, special footwear and other personal protective equipment in oil and gas production.

No. 267 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 12, 2000 "On revision and development of regulatory documents on labor protection" (a collection of decisions of the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2000, No. 7, Article 39) and No. 153 of July 20, 2010 "On Further Improvement of the Regulatory Legal Framework for Labor Protection" (legislative documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan collection, 2010, No. 28-29, Article 234), I order:

1. Sample standards for free provision of special clothing, special shoes and other personal protective equipment in oil and gas production should be approved in accordance with the appendix.

2. This order shall enter into force ten days after its state registration in the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Based on the above regulations, different uniforms are issued depending on the workplace.

- Oil and gas exploration and production well drilling driller, oil and gas exploration and production well drilling assistant driller, oil and gas exploration and production well drilling assistant driller, mechanical rotary well driller drilling rig, mechanical rotary drilling of wells to the driller's assistant-Tarpaulin suit or waterproof fabric-lined gas suit, tarpaulin boots, tarpaulin gloves, hard hat, helmet worn under the hard hat. In winter, a fleece jacket and trousers with an extra warm lining and felt boots are provided.

- Mining worker working in an open-pit mine, diesel operator-drilling rig operator-Tarpaulin suit, boots or rubber boots, combination gloves, helmet, helmet worn under the helmet. In winter, a fleece jacket and trousers with an extra warm lining and felt boots are provided.

- For well sampler lifting machine- Tarpaulin suit, boots or rubber boots, combined gloves, helmet, helmet worn under the helmet. In winter, a fleece jacket and trousers with an extra warm lining and felt boots are provided.

- Support worker in pipe and tool shed or area (with transport) - Waterproof jacket, leather shoes or boots, tarpaulin gloves, jacket and pants with extra warm winter lining and felt boots is given.

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